

A Possible Occurrence of Delta Rebound During Neurofeedback Training —Clinical Implications From a Case Report

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Abstract: Neurofeedback (NF) has been increasingly applied to post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD); however, the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying its clinical effects remain incompletely understood. This case report describes EEG spectral changes observed during an 11-week course of NF training in a male patient in his 50s diagnosed with PTSD. A low-beta NF protocol was applied (15–18 Hz reward; 2–8 Hz and 22–36 Hz inhibition), and resting-state EEG was recorded during eyes-open resting state and eyes-closed resting state. Spectral analysis was performed using the maximum entropy method (MEM). Following the sixth NF session, a marked but transient increase in delta band power (1–4 Hz) was observed during the eyes-open resting state; this increase subsequently subsided and returned to baseline levels, suggesting a rebound phenomenon rather than a sustained training effect. In contrast, alpha band power (8–12 Hz) during the eyes-closed resting state showed a sustained increase over the course of training. Subjectively, a temporary worsening of symptoms coincided with the delta increase, followed by persistent improvements in sleep stability, disappearance of trauma-related dreams, and enhanced emotional regulation, which were corroborated by clinical evaluation. The transient delta increase was interpreted as a possible delta rebound phenomenon reflecting a transitional phase of NF-induced neural reorganization rather than drowsiness or protocol failure. Although limited to a single case, these findings suggest that NF effects in PTSD may involve dynamic, multi-band EEG adjustments at the network level, warranting further systematic investigation.

Keywords: EEG, Neurofeedback, Delta rebound, Low-beta training, PTSD,

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Electroencephalography and Neurofeedback

Electroencephalography (EEG) reflects synchronized electrical activity generated by neuronal populations in the cerebral cortex and has been associated with distinct physiological and psychological states depending on frequency bands. Although frequency band definitions vary slightly across studies, delta activity (1–4 Hz) is generally associated with low arousal states and sleep, theta activity (4–8 Hz) with internal attention and emotional processing, alpha activity (8–12 Hz) with rest and inhibitory processing, and beta activity (12–30 Hz)

with arousal, attention, and cognitive activity [1]. Neurofeedback (NF) is a form of biofeedback intervention that promotes self-regulation of brain activity by providing real-time feedback based on EEG signals [2]. Auditory feedback, visual feedback, or a combination of both is typically used. Positive feedback is provided when EEG activity meets predefined criteria, whereas negative feedback is delivered when the criteria are not met. NF protocols are designed by reinforcing or inhibiting specific frequency bands, either individually or in combination. The underlying mechanisms of NF are not limited to simple modulation of targeted frequency bands but may involve broader reorganization of neural networks and restoration of self-regulatory functions within the brain [3][4].

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B. Psychotherapy and Neurofeedback

Major psychotherapeutic approaches for psychiatric disorders include person-centered therapy, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), prolonged exposure therapy (PE), and social skills training (SST). These therapies aim to alleviate symptoms through cognitive, emotional, and mnemonic reprocessing and have played an essential role in clinical practice.

However, psychotherapy is largely based on verbal communication and presupposes conscious introspection and recollection, which may impose a substantial burden on patients for whom these processes are difficult. In recent years, NF has gained attention as an intervention that directly targets physiological and neural processes. NF is noninvasive and does not necessarily require verbalization, thereby offering therapeutic characteristics distinct from those of conventional psychotherapies.

C. Application of Neurofeedback in Psychiatry

Neurofeedback has been applied to various psychiatric conditions, including attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), depression, anxiety disorders, and PTSD. In ADHD, NF training has been used to improve attentional control and arousal regulation [5]. In depression, improvements in emotional regulation and psychological distress have been reported. In PTSD, NF has been shown to alleviate symptoms such as hyperarousal, sleep disturbances, and emotional dysregulation [6].

Despite these findings, several challenges remain, including the limited number of randomized controlled trials and the lack of standardized protocols [2][7][8][9]. Moreover, the mechanisms by which self-regulatory processes operate during and after NF training remain insufficiently understood. Additional case-based investigations may therefore contribute to clarifying the neurophysiological processes underlying NF interventions in psychiatric disorders. The present study reports a distinctive case of EEG spectral changes observed during NF training in a patient diagnosed with PTSD.

II. Methods

A. Client

The client was a man in his 50s who had been diagnosed with depression and PTSD and was receiving outpatient treatment at a psychosomatic medicine clinic. The NF training was conducted between May and July 2024. During this period, the client attended monthly medical consultations with a psychiatrist and

counseling sessions with a clinical psychologist. No pharmacological treatment was administered.

NF training was conducted at the client's request after a full explanation of the procedure, and written informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

PTSD is a psychiatric condition characterized by distinctive stress-related symptoms following exposure to life-threatening or severely distressing events [1]. Such events include natural disasters, combat, violence, severe sexual assault, accidents, or abuse. Trauma can result not only from direct threat to one's own safety but also from witnessing such events or learning that close family members have been exposed. Core symptoms include intrusive recollections, avoidance, negative alterations in cognition and mood, and marked changes in arousal and reactivity. A diagnosis of PTSD is made when these symptoms persist for more than one month. Trauma-related stress can induce profound alterations in brain function. Traumatic experiences disrupt neural circuitry by inducing hyperactivity of the amygdala, dysfunction of the prefrontal cortex, and impaired functioning of the cingulate gyrus and hippocampus, thereby contributing to hyperarousal, flashbacks, and dissociation [2]. The prefrontal cortex in particular is involved in fear extinction, salience processing, and mood regulation; abnormal activation of prefrontal circuits has been implicated in the pathophysiology of PTSD [3]. For many individuals, trauma remains a lifelong challenge.

B. EEG Recording

EEG signals were recorded using a two-channel NF amplifier (U-Wiz; Pocket Neurobics, Inc.), and data acquisition was performed with EEGer software (EEGer Inc., EEGer4 version 4.40y). EEG activity was recorded using a monopolar montage. During the initial assessment on May 22, a mini-map recording was conducted with active electrodes placed at Fz, Cz, and Pz according to the international 10–20 system. The reference electrode was placed on the left earlobe, and the ground electrode on the right earlobe.

The sampling rate was set at 256 Hz, and electrode impedance was maintained below 15 k Ω . EEG recordings were obtained for one minute each during the eyes-open resting state and the eyes-closed resting state. All measurements were conducted in a quiet room with the client seated comfortably in a chair. EEG recordings following NF intervention were also obtained at Cz using the same procedure.

C. Neurofeedback Intervention

Neurofeedback training was conducted approximately once per week from May to July 2024, focusing on low-beta frequency band training. Each training session lasted between approximately 3 and 18 minutes. The active electrode was placed at Cz, with the reference electrode on the left earlobe and the ground electrode on the right earlobe.

The NF protocol consisted of a low inhibit band (2–8 Hz), a reward band (15–18 Hz), and a high inhibit band (22–36 Hz). Previous studies have demonstrated the clinical relevance of combining enhancement of low-beta activity, which supports calm attentional states, with inhibition of frequency bands associated with anxiety and hyperarousal [10]. Although sensorimotor rhythm (SMR; 12–15 Hz) training has traditionally been used, these findings suggest that the 15–18 Hz band may also contribute to emotional stability and normalization of sleep–wake rhythms. In the present case, the reward frequency band was set at 15–18 Hz to target nightmare symptoms and irritability, with the aim of promoting emotional stability and a calm but alert state.

Training was conducted in 3-minute segments, with brief breaks and physical condition checks between segments. EEG activity was continuously monitored, and threshold values were adjusted during training. For the reward band (15–18 Hz), thresholds were adjusted to achieve a reward rate—defined as the proportion of time exceeding the threshold—of approximately 65%. For the inhibit bands, thresholds were set such that the proportion of time exceeding the threshold was approximately 20% for 2–8 Hz and 15% for 22–36 Hz. The overall reward rate, defined as the product of the success rates for all three criteria, was maintained above 45%.

Visual and auditory feedback was provided using video games integrated into the EEGer software. When EEG activity met the predefined criteria—reward band activity exceeding the threshold and inhibit band activity remaining below thresholds—the video game progressed and an auditory beep was presented. When the criteria were not met, the game stagnated and the auditory feedback ceased.

Training sessions were conducted in a quiet counseling room within the clinic. The client remained seated with eyes open during training, and room temperature was maintained at approximately 26°C using air conditioning. Training was paused or discontinued if signs of drowsiness or fatigue were observed. Subjective changes since the previous session

and post-training subjective states were assessed verbally before and after each session.

D. EEG Analysis

EEG spectral analysis was performed using the maximum entropy method (MEM), which offers advantages in spectral resolution and stability when analyzing short-duration data segments compared with the fast Fourier transform (FFT). MEM analysis was conducted using MemCalc software (GMS Co., Ltd.). The model order (lag value) was determined based on multiple information criteria, including final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), autoregressive transfer function criterion (CAT), and characteristic correlation time (CCT).

III. RESULTS

A. Changes in EEG Activity

The integrated results combining changes in EEG power values across frequency bands and the client's subjective reports are presented below.

Regarding delta band activity (1–4 Hz), the initial power value during the eyes-open resting state was 10.9 μV^2 . Delta power subsequently decreased on June 5, June 12, and June 19. However, an increase was observed beginning on July 3, and following the sixth NF session on July 10, delta power reached 31.870 μV^2 . One week later, on July 17, the value decreased to 18.254 μV^2 . This marked increase represented a clear elevation compared with previous levels and suggested the presence of a transient rebound phenomenon rather than a sustained change. Delta power subsequently decreased on July 24 and July 31, returning to levels comparable to those observed in June.

Alpha band activity (8–12 Hz) during the eyes-closed resting state demonstrated an overall increasing trend throughout the intervention period, rising from an initial value of 33.110 μV^2 . A pronounced increase was observed on July 10, reaching 80.690 μV^2 , which coincided temporally with the period of increased delta band activity.

In contrast, beta band activity including the trained reward band (15–18 Hz) did not increase. The broader 12–18 Hz beta band instead exhibited a slight decreasing trend. During the eyes-open resting state, beta power decreased from 5.993 μV^2 at the initial measurement to 2.439 μV^2 on July 31. A similar pattern was observed during the eyes-closed resting state.

High-frequency bands (18–22 Hz and 22–32 Hz) showed slight decreases across the entire training

period under both eyes-open and eyes-closed resting conditions.

Table1 Results of EEG Power Spectral Analysis at Each Session During Eyes-Open State

Session date	Interval Integral Power Spectral Density						
	0.5-1Hz	1-4Hz	4-8Hz	8-12Hz	12-18Hz	18-22Hz	22-32Hz
May 22 (BaseLine)	1.915	10.902	8.701	6.635	5.993	3.070	4.549
May 29	2.714	15.013	8.432	6.027	4.007	2.408	6.373
June 5	1.683	8.772	6.388	9.967	5.041	2.991	5.026
June 12	1.062	6.058	5.667	6.058	2.784	1.365	2.223
June 19	2.209	7.469	6.629	8.981	3.269	1.351	2.545
July 3	2.219	10.201	7.154	9.736	2.958	1.920	2.295
July 10	5.126	31.870	11.692	6.364	4.155	2.027	5.583
July 17	1.559	18.254	10.055	7.813	3.416	1.460	2.729
July 24	0.924	8.253	6.731	5.721	2.893	1.079	2.170
July 31	1.267	7.835	5.778	6.081	2.429	1.182	2.303

Table2 Results of EEG Power Spectral Analysis at Each Session During Eyes-Closed State

Session date	Interval Integral Power Spectral Density						
	0.5-1Hz	1-4Hz	4-8Hz	8-12Hz	12-18Hz	18-22Hz	22-32Hz
May 22 (BaseLine)	1.190	8.390	79.560	33.110	8.920	3.590	5.310
May 29	1.200	7.250	14.230	62.560	7.030	3.240	6.870
June 5	0.719	8.060	24.860	54.370	8.140	4.060	7.140
June 12	0.891	7.900	36.560	53.230	6.530	1.950	3.670
June 19	0.871	9.170	66.990	46.670	5.660	1.710	2.460
July 3	1.230	9.540	49.180	46.750	5.930	1.772	2.370
July 10	0.971	7.190	17.920	80.690	6.340	2.460	7.730
July 17	0.981	10.530	49.160	68.750	7.300	2.290	2.930
July 24	1.350	10.590	39.560	56.580	6.780	2.040	4.450
July 31	1.230	8.400	43.190	30.050	5.050	1.570	2.360

Figure1 Changes in 1-4Hz Power Spectral Density During Eyes-Open State

Figure2 Changes in 8-12Hz Power Spectral Density During Eyes-Closed State

B. Changes in Subjective Experience

At the beginning of NF training, the client reported frequent trauma-related dreams and persistent irritability as primary complaints, describing difficulty maintaining a calm emotional state. Following trauma-related dreams, irritability and depressive mood often persisted for several days, imposing a substantial psychological burden.

After initiation of NF training, the client reported “pleasant drowsiness” and a “reduction in trauma-related recollections” on June 12. On July 3, the client stated that “my dreams have changed completely,” indicating the disappearance of trauma-related dreams. However, on July 10, the client reported a temporary worsening, describing the experience as “feeling as though I was back to square one.” This subjective deterioration coincided with the period of increased delta band activity observed following the training session.

Subsequently, emotional stability improved steadily. On July 17, the client reported that “my irritability has become more manageable”, and on July 31 stated that “negative feelings subside quickly and no longer linger.”

During a follow-up interview conducted in December 2025, the client reflected that the changes experienced in July of the previous year were “extremely significant,” emphasizing that the

disappearance of trauma-related dreams had contributed substantially to emotional stabilization. These subjective changes are summarized in Table 3.

In addition to the client’s self-reports, the treating psychiatrist provided a clinical evaluation indicating marked improvement following the NF intervention. Specifically, the psychiatrist noted “overall substantial changes,” highlighting that the client had become able to maintain an appropriate psychological distance from previously rigid and perseverative thought patterns. The clinician also observed that the client had developed a “more self-compassionate way of thinking.”

These observations suggested not only symptom reduction but also qualitative improvements in self-understanding and emotional regulation. During clinical interviews conducted before and after NF training, the client increasingly disclosed past experiences and engaged in positive self-directed verbalizations. As emotional stability improved in late July, these self-directed verbalizations became more consistent, suggesting that the client acquired a more flexible and tolerant self-perception that had previously been difficult to achieve. These changes were consistently noted by both the psychiatrist and the therapist.

Table3 Timeline of Subjective Changes

Date	Client’s Statements
May 22, 2024 (Initial session)	I have trauma-related dreams, and persistent irritability continues. I would like to do something about this irritability first.
June 5, 2024	Since the previous session, I often recall unpleasant events; however, I am able to forget them more quickly.
June 12, 2024	After the previous session, I felt a pleasant drowsiness. The frequency of recalling traumatic memories was lower than the previous week.
June 19, 2024	I sometimes wake up after having strange dreams. I feel that something is changing.
July 3, 2024	My dreams have completely changed. I no longer have dreams related to the trauma.
July 10, 2024	I felt unwell throughout the week. I felt as though I was back to square one. I keep telling myself to stay positive.
July 17, 2024	My irritability has lessened. It fades away smoothly.
July 24, 2024	I truly want to change, and I feel that I am changing. I had a trauma-related dream for the first time in a while, but it did not linger.
July 31, 2024	Even when I feel irritated, my mood settles quickly.
December 8, 2025 (Follow-up)	The complete change in my dreams was particularly significant. Because I no longer dwell on irritability, my overall mood has improved.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this case report, NF training was conducted over an 11-week period in a patient with PTSD, and characteristic changes were observed in both EEG activity and subjective experience. Notable findings included a marked rebound phenomenon in delta band activity during the eyes-open resting state and a sustained increase in alpha band activity during the eyes-closed resting state. These findings are consistent with previous research demonstrating the clinical effectiveness of NF in PTSD and further suggest that its therapeutic effects may not be limited to simple enhancement of targeted frequency bands. Rather, NF may exert its clinical effects through dynamic interactions among multiple frequency bands and reorganization of neural circuits.

A. A Possible Occurrence of Delta Rebound

In the present case, a pronounced increase in delta band power during the eyes-open resting state was observed following the sixth NF session. This increase was transient and did not persist across subsequent measurements, with delta power returning to levels comparable to those observed earlier in the intervention period. Based on this temporal pattern, the observed change was interpreted not as a stable therapeutic effect but as a temporary response occurring during the course of NF training. This phenomenon was therefore designated as a delta rebound phenomenon.

In clinical NF practice, increases in delta band activity are often associated with drowsiness, fatigue, or reduced arousal due to monotonous training tasks. However, in the present case, the client did not report subjective sleepiness or fatigue during the session in which delta activity increased, and no clear behavioral signs of decreased arousal were observed. Furthermore, inhibition rates in the 2–8 Hz band during this session were comparable to those observed in other sessions, making it unlikely that the increase in delta activity resulted from protocol failure or inadequate suppression of low-frequency activity.

The transient increase in delta band activity may therefore reflect processes beyond simple physiological fluctuation. Meerwijk, Ford, and Weiss reported that resting-state delta power correlates with psychological distress in adults with a history of depression [11]. In the present case, the client reported a marked worsening of mood during the period in which delta power peaked,

suggesting that increased delta activity may have reflected heightened emotional burden or distress.

Previous studies of SMR training have reported increases in sleep spindles and delta-like activity [12]. The present findings indicate that similar low-frequency fluctuations may occur even during low-beta enhancement training not restricted to the SMR band. This observation supports the hypothesis proposed by Ros that NF effects may involve large-scale network reorganization rather than isolated modulation of specific frequency bands [3]. The observed delta rebound may therefore represent a transitional phase in broader neural network reconfiguration rather than a direct effect of reinforcing the trained frequency band.

Additionally, alpha rebound phenomena have been reported following alpha desynchronization NF in PTSD, with such rebounds interpreted as reflecting self-normalization of alpha rhythms [13]. Taken together, these findings raise the possibility that a rebound phenomenon analogous to alpha rebound may also occur in the delta band. In this interpretation, the transient increase in delta activity may represent a compensatory response to prior suppression, reflecting an ongoing process of homeostatic reorganization within the brain. This unintended yet potentially clinically meaningful increase in delta band activity—the delta rebound phenomenon—may thus warrant further attention.

B. Delta Rebound and Changes in Sleep

Kolk identified disrupted sleep architecture and recurrent nightmares as core symptoms of PTSD, and abrupt fluctuations in delta band activity may capture neurophysiological correlates of these sleep-related disturbances [6]. Sleep and EEG studies of PTSD have reported reductions in slow-wave sleep and low-frequency activity, as well as increased sleep fragmentation, suggesting dysregulation of sleep-modulatory mechanisms [14].

In the present case, subjective improvements in sleep occurred around the period in which the delta rebound phenomenon was observed. Although a temporary worsening of psychological state was reported at the time of peak delta activity, this phase was followed by sustained stabilization of sleep and persistent disappearance of trauma-related dreams. Delta band activity is closely associated with slow-wave activity during sleep; however, recent studies suggest that delta activity observed during wakefulness may also be related to sleep–wake regulation and homeostatic processes [12][15].

From this perspective, the delta rebound observed during the eyes-open resting state may not simply reflect reduced arousal or fatigue but rather a reorganization of sleep–wake regulatory systems induced by NF training. Notably, the delta rebound occurred during the eyes-open resting state rather than during the eyes-closed resting state. This pattern suggests that the phenomenon may reflect recalibration of regulatory mechanisms operating during wakefulness rather than sleep itself. The persistence of improved sleep quality following this phase further supports the interpretation that this transient rebound contributed to subsequent stabilization of sleep function.

C. Increase in Alpha Band Activity During the Eyes-Closed Resting State

Alpha band activity has long been a central focus in NF training and has been associated with relaxation and inhibition of sensory input [16][17][18]. Alpha rhythms are particularly prominent during the eyes-closed resting state and are considered to reflect a stable cortical activation state [16]. Increases in eyes-closed alpha activity are often interpreted as indicators of autonomic and cortical stabilization during wakefulness.

In the present case, progression of NF training was accompanied by subjective reports such as disappearance of trauma-related dreams and increased sleep duration. These subjective changes closely corresponded with increases in resting-state alpha activity. This parallel suggests an association between NF-induced neurophysiological changes and subjective improvements in sleep. In PTSD, nightmares are thought to be related to impaired nocturnal emotional processing and persistent hyperarousal [19]. NF training may have contributed to recalibration of arousal and emotional regulation systems, thereby alleviating hyperarousal symptoms and facilitating stabilization of sleep and emotional state.

Furthermore, Nicholson demonstrated in a randomized controlled trial that normalization of alpha rhythms contributed to symptom reduction in PTSD through modulation of default mode network (DMN) activity [14]. The parallel increase in alpha activity and symptom improvement observed in the present case is consistent with these findings. The observed alpha increase may therefore reflect not merely enhanced relaxation but a broader neurophysiological change related to sleep regulation, self-regulation, and emotional stability.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings of the present case suggest that NF training may contribute to symptom improvement in PTSD through dynamic modulation of multiple frequency bands rather than simple enhancement of a single target band. Neurophysiological changes observed in this case may underlie clinical effects such as transformation of trauma-related dreams and stabilization of emotional state. The pronounced increase in delta band activity observed during this process was designated as a delta rebound phenomenon. This interpretation supports the perspective proposed by Ros that NF effects should be understood in terms of brain-wide self-organizing mechanisms rather than isolated frequency-specific training effects [20].

The present case also highlights the potential clinical relevance of reinforcing the 15–18 Hz (beta-1) frequency band in PTSD. Compared with SMR training, beta-1 training has been reported to enhance cortical arousal and increase P300 amplitude, thereby facilitating efficient allocation of attentional resources and improved stimulus evaluation [21]. In this case, symptom reduction may have been supported by optimized arousal regulation and smoother cognitive–emotional processing resulting from the beta-1 protocol.

Chiba et al. proposed the potential of decoded NF for PTSD, suggesting that future interventions may target specific neural circuits with greater precision [22]. Randomized controlled trials have already demonstrated the safety and efficacy of NF in PTSD at the group level [6]. The present case provides individual-level support for these findings.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, this report describes a single case without a control condition, limiting generalizability. It remains unclear whether the delta rebound phenomenon is specific to this case or occurs as a secondary effect in other NF interventions. Second, although EEG recordings were obtained following NF sessions, pre-session EEG measurements at each session would have allowed for more precise assessment of temporal changes.

Additionally, EEG measurement was limited to central scalp locations, restricting spatial resolution. Future studies should employ broader EEG coverage and incorporate quantitative EEG (QEEG), coherence analysis, functional connectivity analysis, or functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to examine network-level mechanisms underlying the delta rebound phenomenon. Furthermore, although subjective improvements in sleep—particularly disappearance of trauma-related dreams—appeared to play a major role in symptom alleviation, sleep EEG measurements were not obtained. Objective assessment of sleep architecture

would enable more rigorous evaluation of NF effects on sleep.

To enhance objectivity, future research should also incorporate standardized psychological measures and conduct long-term follow-up assessments to evaluate the durability of neurophysiological and psychological changes.

Despite these limitations, the present study suggests a novel perspective on NF training and highlights its potential to induce clinically meaningful neurophysiological transitions. Further investigation is warranted to clarify the mechanisms and generalizability of the delta rebound phenomenon.

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